

oLIVER STATUS

Aim

The aim of the oLIVER project is to apply APTA-SHAPE to identify biomarkers of NAFLD for the development of strategies for:

- Detection of NASH.
- Monitoring of disease progression and treatment response.
- Stratification of fibrosis stage.

Introduction

Initially, a large library of aptamer nano sensors was created capable of broad-scale targeting of plasma components from blood samples of NAFLD patients (termed APTA-SHAPE panel training).

1 uL of plasma from 78 blood samples of NASH patients was subsequently profiled to identify aptamer signals either upregulated or downregulated in correlation to progression of fibrosis stage (termed APTA-SHAPE sample profiling / branched selection). Plasma components for profiling were immobilized on NHS-magnetic beads.

Aptamer signals were obtained by sequencing the RNA sequence and the results of the profiling of each sample. A total of 628 million aptamer reads across the 78 samples were obtained and processed by the software BION by Niels Larsen. These were used for training the computer model.

Separately, 72 samples with a total of 246 million reads from a separate cohort were processed as above as a validation cohort.

Overview of metadata.

The distribution of fibrosis in the two cohorts. We see that the training samples generally have a higher fibrosis score than the validation samples.

Figure 1: The distribution of fibrosis stage in the training and validation cohort. Fibrosis stage 0: no fibrosis, fibrosis stage 1: mild fibrosis, fibrosis stage 2: moderate fibrosis, fibrosis stage 3: severe fibrosis and fibrosis stage 4: cirrhosis.

QC analysis

The number of missing values is calculated as a function of the rank of the aptamer. As the overall abundance falls the chance of a sequence having a missing value increase. Shown below are the training set on the left and the validation set on the right.

In this case the number of aptamers with missing values starts increasing around rank 200 for the validation set. Therefore, only the 200 most abundant aptamers were considered in the training data.

Figure 2: Missing values in the aptamer data as a function of the rank of the aptamer. Training (Left), Validation (Right)

Exploratory Data analysis

As an attempt to explore the data, principal component analysis (PCA) was used on the aptamer binding data. We observe that the separation on the second principal component (PC2) correlates to the progression of fibrosis, indicating that we may predict fibrosis with this data set. To further illustrate this, the PC2 values are plotted on a boxplot, which show statistically significant differences between no fibrosis and advanced fibrosis and cirrhosis (fibrosis stage 3 and 4). Similar differences were found between samples with mild and moderate fibrosis (fibrosis stage 1 and 2) compared to advanced fibrosis and cirrhosis (fibrosis stage 3 and 4).

Figure 3: PCA plot of the training cohort. Unsupervised dimensional reduction shows a fibrosis stage dependent separation on the second principal component.

Figure 4: The PC2 coordinate shown as a boxplot shows a gradual increase in PC2 correlating with advancement in stage of fibrosis. With a statistically significant separation between no fibrosis and severe fibrosis and cirrhosis (fibrosis stage 3 and 4), and between mild fibrosis and moderate (fibrosis stage 1 and 2) and severe fibrosis and cirrhosis (fibrosis stage 3 and 4).

Differential binding analysis

Each aptamer in the training set is now tested for differential binding using a t-test. An aptamer is considered significantly differentially expressed if the p-value adjusted with Benjamini-Hochberg method was below 0.05. The fold change and p-value are shown in the volcano plot below. Since the validation data set only contains samples with no fibrosis and mild or moderate fibrosis, only these samples are considered in the training of the model and the severe fibrosis or cirrhosis cases are discarded.

Figure 5: Ordinary least square regression for each aptamer between no fibrosis and mild and moderate fibrosis. Aptamers with a Benjamini-Hochberg adjusted p-value below 0.05 were deemed significant.

18 aptamers were found to have differential binding between no fibrosis and mild or moderate fibrosis samples.

To visualize the difference between the samples in the validation dataset a PCA is run and a statistical test on the PC1 of the validation data is performed, showing the largest variation between samples using these aptamers were the advancement of fibrosis stage. Since we cannot assume that the coordinates are normally distributed the test used is a Wilcoxon ranked test.

Figure 6: Using aptamers found in figure 5, samples with no fibrosis and mild fibrosis could be separated on the first principal component. This shows an statistical significant difference between sample types in the validation cohort.

Doing this a p-value of 0.0087 was found between the two categories, showing a strong statistically significant difference between samples with no fibrosis and samples with mild or moderate fibrosis.

Figure 7: Using aptamers found in figure 5 samples with no fibrosis and mild fibrosis could be separated on the first principal component, with an AUC of 0.77.

Another way to quantify this is using an ROC curve and calculating the AUC-value. If done on the samples with no fibrosis vs. the samples with mild fibrosis we find an AUC value of 0.77.

Future work

Working on the training cohort it was found that the APTASHAPE technique holds potential to distinguish between the samples with no fibrosis and mild or moderate fibrosis. The targets of the aptamers responsible for this change should be identified, and additional validation Samples from patients with more advanced fibrosis stage should be tested.